

species so far, we undertook a systematic chemical investigation of the leaves of the plant.

The air-dried powdered leaves (0.5 kg) of *S. vestita* (collected from Araku valley near Visakhapatnam) were exhaustively extracted with petroleum ether, benzene and methanol. Concentration of petroleum ether extract afforded a pale yellow solid which on crystallisation from methanol gave colourless needles, m.p. 235–37°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 25.35^\circ$ (methanol) which was identified as dihydromyricetin (1) from its uv, ir, ^1H nmr and mass spectra. The benzene extract on column chromatography over silica gel and elution with benzene-chloroform (1 : 1) furnished colourless crystalline needles, m.p. 245–46°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} - 19.6^\circ$ (methanol) and was identified as naringenin (2) from its uv, ir, ^1H nmr, mass spectral data and also by direct comparison with an authentic sample. The chloroform-methanol (1 : 1) eluent gave a colourless crystalline solid, m.p. 170–71°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 89.5^\circ$ (ethanol), which on acid hydrolysis gave an aglycone identical in all respects to 2, and two sugars characterised as D-glucose and L-rhamnose. Identity of the compound as naringin (3) was confirmed from its uv, ^1H nmr and mass spectral data and also by usual comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir). The concentrated methanol extract on cooling gave a yellow solid which was repeatedly crystallised from methanol to yield yellow needles, m.p. 357–58°, and was characterised as myricetin (4) from its colour reactions, uv data and by direct comparison with an authentic sample (m.m.p. and co-tlc).

Dihydromyricetin (1) is a rare member of the dihydroflavonol family, which has been found in relatively few plant species. Incidentally, this is the second report of its occurrence from Leguminosae family, the earlier report was from *Adenanthera pavonina*³.

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Phytochemical Examination of the Leaves of *Shutteria vestita*

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SHUTERIA vestita Wight. and Arn.¹ (Leguminosae) is closely related to species of *Cologania* and *Dumasia*². Since no work has been reported on this

References

1. O. N. ALLEN and E. K. ALLEN, "The Leguminosae—A Source Book of Characteristics, Uses and Nodulation", University of Wisconsin Press, Wisconsin, 1981, p. 608.
2. J. S. GAMBLE, "Flora of Presidency of Madras", BSI, Calcutta, 1957, Vol. 1, p. 247.
3. A. GENNARO, L. MERLINI and G. NASINI, *Phytochemistry*, 1972, 11, 1515.